

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

Nathalie Rathkamp (2025): Review of Swarthmore College (2011): Global Nonviolent Action Database (published on Discuss Data), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/65010EAC-7372-4BDC-918A-C447333E2018>

Abstract

The Global Nonviolent Action Database is a project of the Swarthmore College. It reports on cases of nonviolent protest actions taken across the globe (100+ countries) (1), including cases dating back as far as the 12th century BCE all the way up to 2019 (Lakey 2011a). The dataset takes the form of both case studies as well as a more visual representation in the form of an interactive map (1). The researchers decided on the following definition to define what constitutes as a nonviolent action in this database: “[A] technique of struggle that goes beyond institutionalized conflict procedures like law courts and voting, procedures common in many countries. We study the methods of protest, noncooperation, and intervention that typically heighten a conflict – and the use of these methods without the threat or use of injurious force to others. Our definition is not located in the discourse of morality and ethics, although some people may choose to use nonviolent action for ethical reasons. Instead, we focus descriptively on what people do when they use this specific ‘technique of struggle.’” (Lakey 2011c). Of the 1.300+ total entries in this dataset, there are 40 events listed for the countries of Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia covered by Discuss Data. As of summer 2024, it is not clear whether work on the data collection is continuing. The data review includes a link to the official Global Nonviolent Action Database website, from which all the data as well as all information listed here is accessible. However, while the data is freely viewable on the website, it seems that the data is not available for download.

Licensed as Attribution and Share Alike: Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL) (“share-alike”)

Data Review - Global Nonviolent Action Database

The Global Nonviolent Action Database is a project of the Swarthmore College. It reports on cases of nonviolent protest actions taken across the globe (100+ countries) (1), including cases dating back as far as the 12th century BCE all the way up to 2019 (Lakey 2011a). The dataset takes the form of both case studies as well as a more visual representation in the form of an interactive map (1). The researchers decided on the following definition to define what constitutes as a nonviolent action in this database: “[A] *technique of struggle that goes beyond institutionalized conflict procedures like law courts and voting, procedures common in many countries. We study the methods of protest, noncooperation, and intervention that typically heighten a conflict – and the use of these methods without the threat or use of injurious force to others. Our definition is not located in the discourse of morality and ethics, although some people may choose to use nonviolent action for ethical reasons. Instead, we focus descriptively on what people do when they use this specific “technique of struggle.”*” (Lakey 2011c).

The cases in this dataset focus on completed campaigns of nonviolent actions, not movements. Movements often consist of a number of different campaigns, which can be seen by looking at the “civil rights movement” as an example. One of these campaigns was the Montgomery Bus Boycott. So, while the “civil rights movement” does not constitute a case in this dataset, the Montgomery Bus Boycott does (Lakey 2011e). The source material from which the information in this dataset is compiled includes scholarly studies, newspaper accounts, first-person descriptions and entries in history books (Lakey 2011f).

The researchers identify the cases in this dataset via two major factors: The issue that the campaigners are struggling about as well as the goal that the nonviolent action is used for. Six main issues were identified: democracy, economic justice, environment, human rights, national/ethnic identity (including anti-colonial struggles) and peace, which in this case includes all nonviolent actions aiming to reduce the level of violence/injurious force (Lakey 2011b). In terms of goals, three main applications for the nonviolent action were identified: (A) change, which usually means that the campaigners have some sort of reform goal, and in some cases even the goal of a revolution. (B) Defense, is applied in defence of something valued against the threat of change. (C) Third Party Nonviolent Intervention (TPNI), is the intervention of a third party to reduce the level of violence of a conflict. This category can however be further divided into four sub-categories: Accompaniment, interposition, observation/monitoring and presence. For information on these sub-categories please refer to Lakey 2011d (Lakey 2011d).

The main method utilized to analyse the cases, besides the above listed categorizations, is Gene Sharp’s classification of 198 methods of nonviolent actions (published in his book *The Politics of Nonviolent Action* in 1973). Sharp identified three major categories: Intervention, non-cooperation and protest & persuasion, with each section having its own subcategories (for

more information on these sub-categories please refer to Lakey 2011i). Intervention refers to actions that are more directly confrontive, while noncooperation is usually less so. Both of these categories can however be coercive, meaning they can make it impossible for an opponent to rule or carry out their politics. Protest and persuasion on the other hand utilises methods that are less confrontive (Lakey 2011i).

Other variables that were focused on during the coding of the cases are factors such as (a) leader, partners, allies, (b) time of their joining/exiting the campaign, (c) the degree of success of the campaign (rates the success or failure of a campaign with a score from one to ten) and (d) the violence by campaigners and nonviolent action by opponent (defines possible unplanned violence that may have taken place as well as unusual actions by opponents) (Lakey 2011h).

The use of this dataset enables the user to explore connections and patterns within cases of nonviolent action made visible through the easy to navigate interface of the Global Nonviolent Action Database. The database also depicts a wide range of both cultures and ethical backgrounds as well as possible effects these might have had on cases (Lakey 2011g). However, it is to note that while the database covers 100+ countries, it has a very strong focus on the US with them being in first place in terms of entries listed with 420 results. Second place is held by Canada with only 59 results listed. This difference in the number of results clearly shows that the majority of the database entries focus on the US. A further limitation of the dataset, as stated on their website, is the variable quality of information available in the different cases. While collecting data, the team prioritized generating a large variety of cases in order to *“expand the user’s scope, to encourage wider comparisons, and to support creativity and theoretical development.”* (Lakey 2011f), rather than focus on the finer details. However, the team included references in their works to facilitate easier research into the specific cases for the reader (Lakey 2011f).

The dataset can be reached via the official Global Nonviolent Action Database website. For an overview of the data use the “Browse” function. When looking for more specific cases make use of the “Search” function for more filter options. For a more geographical overview, consider using the interactive map.

The Global Nonviolent Action Database is however by no means comprehensive when it comes to the region covered by Discuss Data. As indicated by the table below:

Country	Number of Entries
Russia	11
Ukraine	4
Estonia	3
Kazakhstan	3
Armenia	2
Azerbaijan	2
Belarus	2
Georgia	2
Moldova	2
USSR	2
Kyrgyzstan	2
Latvia	1
Lithuania	1
Tajikistan	1
Turkmenistan	1
Uzbekistan	1
Total Entries	40

Sources:

- (1) Global Nonviolent Action Database. <https://nvdatabase.swarthmore.edu/>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.
- (2) George Lakey 2011a. About the Database. <https://nvdatabase.swarthmore.edu/content/about-database>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.
- (3) George Lakey 2011b. Issue Clusters. <https://nvdatabase.swarthmore.edu/content/issue-clusters> Last accessed 27.09.2024.
- (4) George Lakey 2011c. Nonviolent Action Defined <https://nvdatabase.swarthmore.edu/content/nonviolent-action-defined>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.
- (5) George Lakey 2011d. Three Applications of NVA. <https://nvdatabase.swarthmore.edu/content/blue-applications-nonviolent-action>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.
- (6) George Lakey 2011e. Campaigns, Not Movements. <https://nvdatabase.swarthmore.edu/content/campaigns-not-movements>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.
- (7) George Lakey 2011f. Limitations of the Database. <https://nvdatabase.swarthmore.edu/content/limitations-database>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.

- (8) George Lakey 2011g. Uses of the Database.
<https://nvdatabase.swarthmore.edu/content/uses-database-0>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.
- (9) George Lakey 2011h. Coding Definitions.
<https://nvdatabase.swarthmore.edu/content/coding-definitions-0>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.
- (10) George Lakey 2011i. Browse Methods. <https://nvdatabase.swarthmore.edu/browse-methods>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.